

Understanding of dielectric properties of cellulose

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Abstract

The theoretical understanding of structural and optoelectronic properties is well-established for a range of inorganic materials; however, such a robust foundation is, in large part, absent in the case of cellulose. Existing literature reports a wide variance in experimentally observed properties for cellulose phases, which are often in contradiction to each other. Motivated by this, we perform an exhaustive first-principles investigation into the structural and optoelectronic properties of cellulose I_{α} and I_{β} phases. Utilizing exchange-correlation functionals that accurately describe van der Waals interaction and leveraging state-of-the-art density functional theory methods, we strive to present a highly accurate periodic model for the cellulose phases. We integrate the framework of volume-average theory and the potential impact of water sorption to offer insights into the considerable discrepancies seen across different experimental outcomes. Thus, our study provides a reconciliatory perspective, bridging the gap between theoretical calculations and disparate experimental data.

Introduction

The development of electronic structure theory has underscored the potential to predict material properties accurately within mean-field density functional theory (DFT), provided the atomic identities, composition, and structure are known (Zunger 2018). This is particularly proven for inorganic bulk compounds. As a reflection of this prediction ability, several open-access databases (e.g., Materials Project (Jain et al. 2013), AFLOW (Calderon et al. 2015), and Open Quantum Materials Database (OQMD) (Kirklin et al. 2015)) have been developed. These databases are a testament to the synergy of computational techniques and materials science, representing a leap in the DFT approach to material discovery, and have accumulated an impressive volume of computed properties for a vast array of materials, providing a highly valuable resource for researchers and engineers worldwide. By integrating state-of-the-art electronic structure calculations with robust and scalable data frameworks, these resources have significantly expanded our capacity to understand and predict material behavior, accelerating innovation across various fields. We note, however, that such databases are usually scarce on data for organic compounds. This is not surprising, as the structures of organic compounds are often very complex to guess. One of the primary hurdles in the structural characterization of such compounds is accurately determining H atom (usually one of the main elements in the organic compounds) locations. Unlike heavier atoms, which can be more easily “visualized” using X-ray crystallography due to their higher electron densities, low electron density makes H less susceptible to X-ray diffraction (Malyi et al. 2022). Moreover, many organic compounds are not periodic or represented within a partial occupation model (Tilley 2020). For instance, cellulose, one of the most abundant natural polymer organic compounds on Earth, is a fascinating material with a complex structure composed of $\beta(1\rightarrow4)$ linked D-glucose units. This natural polymer consists of a periodic layered structure, interconnected mainly via interchain hydrogen bonds, with van der Waals (vdW) forces playing a vital and dominant role in stacking interactions. The structural complexity of cellulose is further highlighted by its ability to exist in different crystalline forms, with cellulose I_{α} (triclinic, $P1$) and I_{β} (monoclinic, $P2_1$) being the most common forms

(French 2014; Gardiner et al. 1985; Kolpak et al. 1976; Sarko et al. 1974; Sarko et al. 1976). Interestingly, despite numerous studies (French 1978; Nishiyama et al. 2002; Nishiyama et al. 2003; Woodcock et al. 1980), both these phases are described within the partial occupancy structures. For instance, the combined x-ray and neutron diffraction study depicts that the two distinct hydrogen bond arrangements could be found with partial occupancy in the range of 70–80% vs 30 – 20%, corresponding to major and minor fractions of total hydrogen bonding network in cellulose I_{β} , respectively (Nishiyama et al. 2002). In the case of cellulose I_{α} , the partial occupancy range of a minor fraction is higher (45%) (Nishiyama et al. 2003). Indeed, even the development of the first-principles model that accurately identifies the representative non-partial occupancy structure and includes an accurate description of vdW forces is not present, and the available studies have a large discrepancy between DFT and experimental works. For instance, the static dielectric constant of cellulose I_{β} calculated using DFT is 2.5–3.1 (Boström et al. 2014; Thiyam et al. 2015), while the corresponding experimental values range 3.11-15 (Boutros et al. 1978; Hou et al. 2021; Kane 1955; Luca et al. 1938; Mo et al. 2020; Mo et al. 2019; Zeng et al. 2016). All this raises the question: (i) can a comprehensive electronic structure theory for the primary cellulose phases be developed? and (ii) if so, can these models account for the discrepancies observed in previous studies on cellulose properties? Driven by these inquiries, we present an in-depth first-principles analysis of the cellulose I_{α} and I_{β} phases, highlighting their lowest energy structures and optoelectronic characteristics. Through our study, we elucidate the influence of vdW forces and suggest a potential reason for the significant variations in the dielectric constant observed in experimental studies. Importantly, we highlight different factors that can affect materials properties and explain, for instance, a possible origin of the large discrepancy in the experimentally measured and theoretically obtained dielectric constant of the cellulose phases.

Computational Methods

All the electronic structure calculations were performed using the DFT approach and projector augmented wave (PAW) method (Blöchl 1994) as implemented in Vienna *Ab-initio* Simulation Package (VASP) (Kresse et al. 1996a, b; Kresse et al. 1993). An energy cutoff of 550 eV was employed for the plane-wave basis set used in wavefunction expansion. The position and lattice optimization were performed until the forces were less than 0.01 eV/Å. Brillouin zones were sampled using Γ -centered k-points mesh corresponding to 5000 k-points/atom and 10000 k-points/atom for structural relaxation and electronic structure calculations, respectively. To account vdW interaction accurately, the structural relaxation was performed using different levels of dispersion correction methods: optB86b-vdW(Klimeš et al. 2011), optB88-vdW(Klimeš et al. 2009), optPBE-vdW (Klimeš et al. 2009), vdW-DF(Dion et al. 2004), vdW-DF2 (Lee et al. 2010), vdW-DF-cx (Berland et al. 2014), rev-vdW-DF2 (Hamada 2014), and rVV10 (Sabatini et al. 2013) XC functionals. These optimized structures were further employed to accurately describe electronic properties using a revised hybrid HSE06 functional (Krukau et al. 2006). Here, due to computational cost, Γ -centered k-points mesh corresponding to 1000 k-points/atom were used. The frequency-dependent dielectric properties were calculated using independent particle approximation(Gajdoš et al. 2006). The Born effective charge tensors, phonon frequencies, and dielectric permittivity tensors have been

calculated using a variational approach within the framework of density-functional perturbation theory, yielding linear response functions (Baroni et al. 2001; Gonze 1997; Gonze et al. 1992; Gonze et al. 1997).

Results and Discussion

Evaluating H arrangements in cellulose I_α and I_β - identifying the lowest energy configurations

Using available crystallographic data and partial occupancy models (French 2014) for cellulose I_α and I_β phases (Figs. 1a and 1b), we first analyze different H atom arrangements to identify the lowest energy structures. Specifically, using the primitive cells for the partial occupancy models of cellulose I_α and I_β, we screen different arrangements of H atoms corresponding to the C₆H₁₀O₅ chemical formula. All these structures are fully relaxed using optB86b-vdW XC functional (Klimeš et al. 2011). To account for the possibility of various H positioning at the primary alcohol O6 and secondary alcohol O2 sites labeled as in (Nishiyama et al., 2002; Nishiyama et al., 2003), we have analyzed multiple configurations, including atomic arrangements (referred to as “single configured”) where all O6 and O2 form a single O-H bond, as well as atomic arrangements where two H atoms are coordinated to the same O6 or O2 site, referred to as “double coordinated” sites. In total, 125 unique input configurations for cellulose I_α and 174 configurations for cellulose I_β were considered. It should be noted that the stability of the lowest-energy configurations with respect to random atomic displacements has also been confirmed. The results, summarized in Figs. 1c and 1d, show that while different atomic configurations have different energies, the lowest-energy configurations (given in the supplementary materials) for both phases correspond to the atomic arrangement with single configured O sites. This implies that the cellulose structure where the O atoms have double coordination with H atoms is energetically unfavorable. Indeed, the relaxation of such input structures often leads to the desorption of H atoms in the form of H₂ molecule. The lowest energy configuration identified for cellulose I_α and I_β agrees with that found in previous works using different methods (Chen et al. 2014; Nishiyama et al. 2008), showing the reliability of the developed first-principle model.

Structural properties of cellulose I_α and I_β – the role of vdW interaction

The complexity of cellulose structure arises not only from the partial occupancy discussed above but also from the significant effect of vdW interactions on materials properties (Malyi et al. 2018). What makes this even more complex is that while various XC functionals have been developed, there remains no universally accepted XC functional capable of accurately reproducing vdW interactions. This limitation becomes evident especially when compared to the results obtained from diffusion quantum Monte-Carlo calculations (Shulenburger et al. 2015), showing, for instance, the inability of modern XC functionals to reproduce the reference state of charge density distribution in the bilayer black phosphorene systems. Because of this, in practice, one often needs to check the sensitivity of material properties to specific

ways of treatment of vdW interactions and verify that main conclusions are not affected by the choice of the computational setup. Motivated by this, using the lowest energy structures identified above, we calculated structural and electronic properties for cellulose I_{α} and I_{β} phases using different ways to treat vdW forces. The results are summarized in Fig. 2 and, as expected, show variations in lattice constants for different XC functionals. Importantly, the lowest energy cellulose I_{β} and I_{α} structures have β -dextrorotatory-glucose units covalently bonded along the c-direction, with weak vdW interactions along the a and a & b lattice vectors, respectively. This makes the lattice constants along the a and b directions significantly more sensitive to XC functional for both phases. For instance, for cellulose I_{β} , depending on the XC functional (Fig. 2d), the lattice constants varied from 7.01–7.85, 8.11–8.36, and 10.40–10.58 Å for the a, b, and c lattice constants, respectively. Similar variation of lattice constants for cellulose I_{α} structure is also observed (Fig. 2b). It is important to note that our calculations also revealed minor discrepancies in lattice angles compared to experimental findings. This divergence arises primarily because our computational approach allows unrestricted relaxation of the internal structure and lattice vectors. Consequently, assuming that the experimentally detected structures could represent an ensemble average of different low-energy domains is plausible. Alternatively, the variations may be attributed to thermal fluctuations affecting different crystal regions, leading to the occupation of diverse H-bonding arrangements. This would result in an experimentally observed global average structure. In general, however, the computed lattice vectors are comparable to the experimental one. For instance, for cellulose I_{β} structure, the experimentally obtained lattice vectors are $a = 7.64$ Å, $b = 8.18$ Å, $c = 10.37$ Å, and $\gamma = 96.5$ at 15 K and $a = 7.76$ Å, $b = 8.20$ Å, $c = 10.37$ Å, and $\gamma = 96.5$ at 295 K (Nishiyama et al. 2008). As noted above, the accurate description of the vdW system is important not only for describing vdW interaction but also for accurate calculations of the electronic properties (Malyi et al. 2018). Indeed, as we can see, the calculated band gap energies for cellulose I_{β} and I_{α} structures are 5.35–5.54 eV and 5.21–5.47 eV, respectively. We note, however, that vdW-DF functionals are still based on soft XC functionals, which are known to underestimate the band gap energy. Moreover, there is not yet a universally accepted XC functional that can be used to describe both electronic and structural properties at the same time. In practice, such descriptions are often done by applying hybrid functional to calculate band gap energy for the frozen vdW-DF functional-relaxed structures (Yadav et al. 2023). Indeed, in many cases, this method allows for a good description of the electronic band gap energy with high accuracy. Application of such method of calculations in this case results in a range of band gap energy (HSE06) values of 7.23–7.46 eV and 7.15–7.31 eV for cellulose I_{β} and I_{α} structures, respectively. Here, it is worth mentioning that attempts have been made to quantify the experimental band gap energy. Specifically, for cellulose I_{β} , reported experimental band gap energy values fall within the 4.5–5.7 eV range according to multiple studies (Plermjai et al. 2019; Simao et al. 2015; Sriphan et al. 2023). However, it is important to acknowledge that, in general, the prediction of band gap energy for wide band gap insulators using standard absorption techniques is often challenging due to weak absorption, the role of point defects, etc. It should also be noted that our results are comparable to previously reported work using DFT-PBE0, which yielded values of 8.2 eV and 8.1 eV for cellulose I_{α} and I_{β} , respectively (Srivastava et al. 2020).

Optical properties of cellulose I_{α} and I_{β} phases

The dielectric properties of a material play a pivotal role in shaping its interactions with electromagnetic waves, such as light. These properties dictate how a material polarizes in response to an external electric field, affecting light absorption, reflection, refraction, and transmission. At the first-principles level, these properties are often characterized using the complex dielectric function $\epsilon = \epsilon_1 + i\epsilon_2$, which, for instance, can be calculated using the independent particle approximation (Gajdoš et al. 2006). It is worth noting, however, that deriving these properties through calculations is far from straightforward. The complexity of these calculations arises from the need to use large simulation cells, the sum of a wide range of transitions from occupied to unoccupied states within a dense k-point grid, and employ sufficiently accurate methods to predict the optical band gap energy. While, in principle, in selective systems, all this can be done directly, in this work, to minimize computational cost, we perform optical calculations using the scissor-correction technique, as illustrated in Fig. 3a. Specifically, we calculate the imaginary part of the dielectric function using a given XC functional within independent particle approximation. Then, we align the electronic band gap values with those computed by the HSE06 method for the corresponding structure by shifting the imaginary part of the dielectric function (Fig. 3b). It should be noted that due to the difference in k-points density used for HSE06 and other functionals, the scissor correction is calculated using the difference in corresponding band gaps at Γ point. Subsequently, we apply the Kramers–Kronig relations to calculate the real part of the dielectric function. This method has indeed been adopted in previous studies (Blaha et al. 1990; Crovetto et al. 2016; Malyi et al. 2016) and allowed accurate description of the electronic and optical properties of the materials. The results of the calculations for both cellulose phases determined using optB86b-vdW XC functional are shown in Fig. 3c–f, revealing a marked degree of anisotropy in dielectric properties. Specifically, cellulose I_α exhibits a narrower dielectric anisotropy range than cellulose I_β . This distinction becomes particularly evident when assessing the electronic contributions to the dielectric constant (ϵ_∞) along the xx, yy, and zz directions. Using the optB86b-vdW XC functional with scissor correction, the calculated values are 2.59, 2.60, and 2.64 for cellulose I_α , and 2.54, 2.64, and 2.73 for cellulose I_β .

It is important to recognize that in actual experimental samples, the orientation and arrangement of cellulose fibers can vary. As a result, it makes sense to talk about average dielectric function values along various directions. For instance, one can use an average value calculated as, $(\epsilon_{xx} + \epsilon_{yy} + \epsilon_{zz})/3$, as shown in Fig. 3 for different XC functionals. Broadly speaking, the results across various methods are similar. To highlight this, we look at the directional average of the electronic contribution to the real part of the dielectric function, ϵ_1 . We find that the rVV10 functional yields the highest ϵ_∞ values—2.75 and 2.78 for cellulose I_α and I_β , respectively. In contrast, the vdW-DF functional gives values of 2.47 and 2.49 for cellulose I_α and I_β , respectively. As for the imaginary part of the dielectric function, ϵ_2 , its behavior under different vdW-DF methods is evident from the positions of the absorption edge and peaks, which show minor differences in energy values. Here, the vdW-DF-cx relaxed structure in both phases shows a red-shifted edge compared to other XC functionals.

When an electric field is applied to the solid, the dielectric properties of materials are not only defined by the electronic response, but at low frequencies, ions have enough time to move in response to the

changing electric field. Such contribution is usually discussed in a low-frequency regime (i.e., $\epsilon_1(\omega \rightarrow 0)$), which is represented as $\epsilon_0 = \epsilon_\infty + \epsilon_i$, where ϵ_∞ and ϵ_i are an electronic and ionic contribution to the dielectric constant, respectively. The latter can be obtained knowing Born effective charges and the phonon frequencies (Cockayne et al. 2000; Gajdoš et al. 2006; Vali et al. 2004). Using this methodology and the electronic contribution calculated above, we calculated the static dielectric constant for both phases, with results for different XC functionals summarized in Fig. 4c,f. The results show that I_β phase exhibits substantially higher ionic contribution to the dielectric constant. Moreover, the extent to which ions contribute to the dielectric constant in both phases significantly depends on the specific correction techniques used in the computations. Importantly, when using the rVV10 and vdW-DF functionals, the highest and lowest average values for the diagonal ϵ_0 components are found in cellulose I_α (cellulose I_β), with corresponding values of 3.62 (3.72) and 3.17 (3.22), respectively. We note that the computed results for dielectric constant are in the lower range of experimentally reported data 3.11-15.00 (Boutros et al. 1978; Hou et al. 2021; Kane 1955; Luca et al. 1938; Mo et al. 2020; Mo et al. 2019; Zeng et al. 2016).

To gain a deeper understanding of the variability observed in experimental results, we scrutinize the factors that influence material properties during experimental measurements. This scrutiny is especially critical for cellulose structures, given their propensity to absorb substantial amounts of water. Such absorption can significantly alter the material's strength, flexibility, and overall behavior. Additionally, experimental samples may consist of mixed cellulose phases in varying proportions, further complicating the interpretation of results. Consequently, these complexities could result in the experimentally measured properties of cellulose deviating from what might be expected based solely on its chemical formula. Instead, these properties might better reflect a cellulose structure incorporating water molecules or varying proportions of different cellulose phases. While the difference in dielectric constant for cellulose phases cannot explain the nearly 5-fold variation observed in the dielectric constant, the formed effect of water molecules is critical. Indeed, water molecules are polar, on the application of an electric field, the molecule polarizes, leading to the high dielectric constant in the region with sufficient density of water - water is known to have a large static dielectric constant of 76.5–88.2 (Elbaum et al. 1991; Fiedler et al. 2020; Malmberg et al. 1956). Moreover, the presence of water molecules can significantly affect structural property, which can also result in tuning the vdW interaction between the layers (Agarwal et al. 2017; Salmén et al. 2021). In the simplified picture, the effect of water sorption on the dielectric constant can be understood within the so-called volume average theory (Braun et al. 2006; Malyi et al. 2016; Navid et al. 2008), where the effective dielectric constant (ϵ_{eff}) of the composite material containing water with fraction φ and cellulose can be expressed as $\epsilon_{\text{eff}} = (1 - \varphi)\epsilon_c + \varphi\epsilon_w$, where ϵ_c and ϵ_w are dielectric constant of cellulose and water, respectively. In this way, we can see that the increase in water fraction will increase the dielectric constant of the composite material. These results can be directly correlated to experimental measurements with some assumption. Specifically, according to Boutros and Hanna (Boutros et al. 1978), the dielectric properties of cellulose exhibit notable variations with changing moisture levels, assuming that it is directly correlated to the amount of water that can be sorbed by cellulose structure. For instance, they showed that, at frequencies of 10 Mc/sec and a temperature of 25°C, the dielectric constant of cellulose exhibits a progressive increase from 3.11 to 4.59, 5.25, 5.92, and 5.96 as relative

humidity levels rise from 0–35%, 52%, 76%, and 92%, respectively. By seeing these variations, we can infer that the observed differences in the dielectric properties of the experimentally measured cellulose structures can be primarily attributable to the sorption of water molecules. Furthermore, it is reasonable to hypothesize that the lower range of experimentally observed values aligns closely with a dry cellulose structure and, hence, is in close agreement with our DFT results.

Conclusions

Utilizing first-principles calculations, we have comprehensively investigated cellulose I_α and I_β , from predicting the most energetically favorable arrangements of H atoms in the partial occupancy models of both phases to analyzing their optical and electronic properties. Our results confirm that using various XC functionals, coupled with scissors correction, can reliably capture the physics and chemistry of cellulose I_α and I_β with high accuracy. We also reveal the strong phase-dependent anisotropy in dielectric properties. However, due to the complex structure of cellulose samples and thermal disorder, such anisotropy may not be fully detectable experimentally unless single-crystal samples are analyzed. In addition to electronic contributions (computed herein within the independent particle approximation), our work discusses the often-overlooked ionic contributions to the dielectric constants, demonstrating, for instance, the difference in static dielectric constants for the two phases. Furthermore, we bridge the gap between theoretical calculations and a wide range of experimentally obtained dielectric constants by explaining the impact of potential water sorption on the dielectric properties of cellulose phases and its connection to experimental data. Using the framework of volume-average theory, we thus explain the discrepancies observed in different experimental measurements. This reveals that the experimentally measured dielectric properties often do not correspond to an ideal, dry cellulose structure but are significantly influenced by water sorption. This work thus offers a valuable benchmark for future experimental/theoretical studies and highlights the need for careful control of environmental factors (e.g., humidity), especially in cases requiring specific dielectric properties.

Declarations

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Ethical Approval Not applicable

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Figures

Figure 1

Identification of the lowest energy H configurations for cellulose I_α and I_β structures. Experimentally proposed crystal structures representing H arrangement in the (a) cellulose I_α and (b) cellulose I_β (French 2014) demonstrating partial H occupancy at O6 and O2 sites. Relative energy distribution for different H configurations in (c) cellulose I_α and (d) I_β. The relative energy in (c) and (d) represents the energy difference with respect to the lowest energy configurations. The green, red, and black spheres in the (a)

and (b) represent C, O, and H atoms, respectively. The white region on H atoms displays their partial occupancy at the specific site according to partial occupancy models (French 2014).

Figure 2

Structural and electronic properties of cellulose I_α and I_β calculated using different XC functionals. Electronic band gap energy computed for (a) cellulose I_α and (c) I_β using different XC functional and HSE06 applied on the top of the structure obtained with the corresponding XC functionals.

Corresponding lattice parameters computed with different XC functionals as compared to the experimental one for (b) cellulose I_α and (d) I_β. The experimental data are taken from (Nishiyama et al. 2008; Nishiyama et al. 2003).

Figure 3

Calculation of dielectric properties for cellulose I_α and I_β structures. Schematic representation of scissor correction in (a) electronic band structure and (b) frequency-dependent dielectric function ϵ_2 . (c,e) real part and (d, f) imaginary part of dielectric function of cellulose I_α and I_β phases computed using optB86b-vdW XC functional with corresponding scissor correction.

Figure 4

Summary of dielectric properties for cellulose I_α and I_β structures computed using different XC functionals. Frequency-dependent average (a,d) real and (b,e) imaginary parts of dielectric functions of cellulose I_α and I_β. Summary of calculations for static dielectric constant, including electronic and ionic contributions, as calculated using different XC functionals for cellulose (c) I_α and (f) I_β.

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